

Deliverable D5.3

Final Impact Assessment Report

Work Package: WP 5, D5.3 Final Impact Assessment Report

Grant Agreement Number: 101094766

Due date of deliverable: 31/01/2026

Actual submission date: 22/01/2026

Start date of project: 01/02/2023 (36 months)

Dissemination Level: public (PU)

Deliverable Lead: Zentrum für Soziale Innovation, ZSI

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Deliverable Information

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Status	<input type="checkbox"/> Plan <input type="checkbox"/> Draft <input type="checkbox"/> Working <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Final <input type="checkbox"/> Approved
Abstract (for public dissemination only)	<p>This document summarizes the insights from the evaluation and impact assessment across the different case studies in the GREAT project. It builds on the evaluation framework defined in Deliverable D5.1 and presents the findings along five impact dimensions: participants, scientific, economic, and societal. We clearly find impact traces across all four dimensions. Across the GREAT case studies there is strong evidence that game-based interventions can enhance climate awareness, support deliberative discussion, and generate valuable insights into public attitudes, emotions, and behaviours related to climate change.</p>
Keywords	Evaluation, impact assessment
Statement of originality	<p>This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise.</p> <p>Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both.</p>

Version History

Version	Date	Comment
0.1	05.05.2025	Draft 0.1 document created, and main structure and first content added
0.2	31.10.2025	Methodology, data overview, first results from case studies included
0.3	15.12.2025	Content added from some of the case studies
0.4	7.01.2026	Input from Beat the Heat case study
0.5	19.01.2026	Ready for Peer review
1.0	21.01.2026	Final edits

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List of Abbreviations

CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
DiBL	Dilemma-based Learning Game (a product of the GREAT partner Serious Games Interactive)
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EESD	Education for the Environment and Sustainable Development
ESD	Education for Sustainable Development
ETEK	Cyprus Scientific and Technical Chamber
GCS	GREAT Case Study
GREAT	Games Realising Effective Affective Transformation
ISCED	International Standard Classification of Education
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NPO	Nonprofit Organisation
NWU	North-West University
OER	Open Educational Resource
UKRI	United Kingdom Research & Innovation
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
UoB	University of Bolton
ROI	Return of Investment
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SGI	Serious Games Interactive
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
WP	Work Package
ZSI	Zentrum fuer Soziale Innovation (Centre for Social Innovation)

1 Executive Summary

The GREAT project (Games Realising Effective Affective Transformation) investigates the potential of game-based approaches to foster political and social engagement with climate change. By embedding interactive and playful methods into climate-related discourse, the project aims to reduce participation barriers, stimulate reflection, and strengthen connections between citizens, policymakers, and other societal stakeholders. Through a diverse portfolio of case studies implemented across educational, policy, civic, and commercial gaming contexts, GREAT has explored how different game formats can support inclusive and participatory approaches to climate action.

This final impact assessment synthesises findings from multiple GREAT case studies conducted throughout the project lifecycle, including large-scale PlanetPlay surveys embedded in commercial games, dilemma-based learning interventions using the DiBL platform in schools, participatory data workshops, and public engagement activities. Building on the evaluation framework defined in Deliverable D5.1, impacts are assessed across four key dimensions: **participant**, **scientific**, **economic**, and **societal**.

Across these dimensions, the findings provide evidence that game-based interventions can enhance climate awareness, support deliberative discussion, and generate valuable insights into public attitudes, emotions, and behaviours related to climate change. At the participant level, the results show that game-based approaches can foster learning, reflection, and engagement, often strengthen efficacy beliefs, and motivate behavioural intentions. While the depth and persistence of these effects vary depending on context, audience characteristics, and facilitation quality, the overall evidence confirms that games can create accessible and meaningful entry points for engagement with complex climate issues.

From a scientific perspective, GREAT contributes to ongoing research on participatory and game-based methods by advancing innovative approaches to data collection, analysis, and citizen involvement. Large-scale game-embedded surveys demonstrated the feasibility of reaching audiences that are typically underrepresented in traditional research and consultation formats, while participatory data workshops illustrated the value of involving citizens not only as respondents but also as co-analysts of data. These approaches have generated new research questions,

methodological insights, and rich datasets that inform both academic research and policy-relevant knowledge production.

The economic dimension highlights both opportunities and challenges. The project demonstrates the potential for game-based engagement to support new value propositions for the games industry, including socially responsible game design, enhanced understanding of player communities, and innovative engagement models. At the same time, the findings underline that economic sustainability beyond the project duration depends on careful design choices, credible messaging, and strategic partnerships with policy institutions, NGOs, and industry actors. Not all audiences welcome climate-related content in games, and reputational and design risks must be managed carefully.

At the societal level, GREAT shows that game-based approaches can complement traditional participation and consultation methods by offering engaging, flexible, and scalable formats for public dialogue. The project successfully engaged a wide range of stakeholders, including citizens, educators, policymakers, NGOs, and game developers, and provided evidence that such approaches can support awareness-raising, community engagement, and policy-oriented reflection. However, the findings also reveal persistent challenges related to inclusivity, as participation across several case studies was uneven with respect to age, gender, and digital access.

In conclusion, the final impact assessment confirms that game-based participation is a promising and flexible tool for climate engagement, capable of generating meaningful individual, scientific, economic, and societal impacts. To maximise long-term value, future efforts should focus on increasing demographic diversity, refining facilitation and design practices, strengthening stakeholder partnerships, and embedding game-based approaches more systematically into policy consultation, education, and community-driven climate action.

2 Introduction

This deliverable presents the final impact assessment conducted within Work Package 5 (WP5) of the GREAT project. Its primary purpose is to document how the project's activities contributed to change across different stakeholder groups and contexts, and to assess these contributions against the objectives and assumptions defined at the outset of the project. The impact assessment builds on the evaluation framework developed in Deliverable D5.1 (Koller et al., 2024), which defined a theory-informed approach to assessing change across multiple levels. Rather than focusing solely on outputs or short-term results, the framework emphasises pathways of impact and the conditions under which different forms of impact may emerge. This perspective is particularly relevant for complex, participatory, and exploratory interventions such as game-based engagement, where outcomes are shaped by context, facilitation, audience composition, and stakeholder collaboration.

The report draws on evidence from a selected set of GREAT case studies that were completed or sufficiently advanced during the later phases of the project. These case studies span a range of formats and settings, including dilemma-based learning games, participatory workshops, and large-scale digital surveys embedded in commercial games. While differing in scale and implementation, all case studies were designed to test how game-based approaches can engage citizens and stakeholders in climate- and sustainability-related issues.

Methodologically, the impact assessment follows a mixed-methods approach. Quantitative data from surveys are combined with qualitative material from open-ended responses, interviews, workshop documentation, and reflective sessions within the consortium. The analysis relies on systematic triangulation of these data sources to capture both measurable patterns and more nuanced forms of change, such as shifts in perspectives, attitudes, learning processes, and collaborative practices. In addition, stakeholder reflections are used to contextualise findings and to identify enabling factors and constraints affecting impact.

The structure of the report reflects this approach. Following this introduction, the document provides an overview of the GREAT case studies included in the assessment, describes the data sources and analytical methods, and then presents results organised along the four impact dimensions defined in the evaluation framework: participant, scientific, economic, and societal. The final sections discuss cross-cutting insights, limitations, and implications according to the main

stakeholder groups, and outline conclusions relevant for future research, policy engagement, and the further development of game-based participatory methods.

By focusing on impact pathways, methodological reflection, and contextual conditions, this introduction sets the scene for a detailed and evidence-based assessment of what the GREAT project has achieved, how these achievements came about, and what can be learned for future initiatives using game-based approaches in sustainability and climate action contexts.

3 Overview of GREAT Case Studies

A complete and detailed overview of the GREAT Case Studies (GCS) is included in the deliverable D4.3. Here we provide a quick overview of which GCS were included in the evaluation and impact assessment of WP5 and which deliverables they are covered (D5.2 and/or D5.3). The case studies, as well as the underlying GREAT approaches, are briefly presented in the following sections.

Table 1: Overview of GREAT case studies

Case Study	Context	Status and Reference
GCS1 UNDP Exploratory	Feasibility study on climate attitudes; initial dataset from diverse geographies; PlanetPlay	Completed; D5.2
GCS2 Waterwise	Interactive DiBL session followed by an embedded PlanetPlay survey on water consumption in the UK	DiBL completed; D5.3
GCS3 Green Jobs	DiBL school interventions in Austrian secondary schools on the topic of green jobs	Completed; D5.2
GCS4 Green Roofs	DiBL intervention with local citizens in Cyprus on green rooftops and urban greening	Completed, D5.2
GCS5 UNDP Play2Act 1	Global PlanetPlay survey launched in popular games together with UNDP on climate responses and the potential of green games	Mostly covered in D5.2; only data workshops covered in D5.3
GCS6 New Automotive	Initial concept design for a UK-Germany comparative engagement on electric vehicle adoption	Did not go forward after its initial stage
GCS7 Prosper	DiBL card game on SDGs implemented with university students in South Africa	Completed; D5.3
GCS8 Play2Act2	Global PlanetPlay survey launched in popular games, including open-ended questions	Completed; D5.3
GCS9 Play2Act3	Global PlanetPlay survey launched in popular games, including open-ended questions	Ongoing
GCS10 Beat The Heat	DiBL intervention in schools in Cyprus on measures to adapt to extreme high heat	Ongoing; D5.3

3.1 Game-Based Approaches in GREAT

Before presenting the GREAT case studies, we first outline the project's distinctive game-based approaches. These approaches characterised the design of the case studies and support the interpretation of the results discussed in this final impact assessment report. GREAT employed

two main game-based methods across its case studies: the dilemma-based intervention and the PlanetPlay survey approach, each associated with a specific platform.

The **dilemma-based intervention** supports structured, group deliberation through short stories, role-play, dilemmas, and participatory prompts. It is usually run in person and facilitated through the DiBL (dilemma-based learning) web platform. This method encourages participants to engage with complex climate challenges and policy questions, generating in-depth qualitative insights, opinions, and ideas. Throughout this report, we will refer to this game-based approach using the acronym “DiBL”.

The **PlanetPlay survey approach** leverages the wide reach of existing commercial digital games on mobile, computer, and console platforms by embedding brief surveys within them. This allows engagement with large and diverse groups of players worldwide, though individual responses are generally less detailed due to the short survey format. The surveys covered several topics, but a key focus in the PlanetPlay case studies reported here was to explore how players experience and perceive **green game content** (also see Harris, 2025; Harris et al., 2025 for case study reports).

In this context, **green game content** refers to any game features, narratives, or design elements that address environmental, sustainability, or climate-related themes. Such content may include messages that raise awareness of environmental issues, gameplay mechanics that involve managing natural resources or responding to climate challenges, storylines centred on ecological crises, or links to external information about sustainability themes. The PlanetPlay surveys did not expose players to specific “green games” or preselected materials; instead, they invited respondents to reflect on their own previous experiences with such content in any games they had played. This clarification is important because all digital games could serve as distribution channels for the surveys, regardless of whether they contained green content themselves. The survey questions therefore asked players about past encounters with green game content rather than reactions to any specific stimulus presented during the study.

3.2 GCS2 Waterwise

The Waterwise case study engaged the public in water sustainability and environmental decision-making. Structured in two interconnected phases, the case study explores how playful and

participatory approaches can bridge personal reflection, collective decision-making, and policy engagement around water management.

During Phase 1, participants engaged thoughtfully with different formats, particularly the dilemma game (DiBL) and data exploration task, and expressed strong preferences for water-saving policies aligned with fairness, collective benefit, and shared responsibility. The activities prompted reflection on personal habits, the impact of infrastructure choices, and the interplay between individual and collective action. Participants used a pre-prepared system diagram of water use to reflect on priorities and interventions, generating a rich set of qualitative and quantitative data, including prioritised policy preferences, individual responses to collective dilemmas, and written reflections. Their contributions highlighted public assumptions and value orientations around water use and governance.

In this deliverable, we only cover this first phase of the project, as the second phase, which includes a digital survey delivered via the PlanetPlay platform and a Game Jam engaging students in participatory design, is still ongoing while we are writing this report.

3.3 GCS5 UNDP Play2Act 1 – Data Workshops

The UNDP Play2Act 1 case study, its PlanetPlay survey method, and results were presented in D5.2 Mid-term Evaluation Report (Koller et al., 2025). The case study involved a global survey distributed through more than 30 game studios, reaching about one million gamers, of whom around 180,000 completed it. The survey asked about players' motivations, experiences, and views on how video games can help address climate change and environmental issues. It also offered respondents the opportunity to sign up for the PlanetPlay platform to learn more information on climate action and opportunities for future engagement.

Gamers who registered on the PlanetPlay platform were later invited by the ZSI team to take part in the follow-up activities, the so-called *Data Workshops*, described in this report. Due to low turnout, students from the GREAT Partner UoB were invited to a second round of workshops. These follow-up activities consisted of participatory *Data Workshops* that used game elements – in the spirit of the GREAT approach – to engage participants with the Play2Act 1 dataset. Guided by the ZSI team as facilitators, participants developed research questions, collectively analysed the

data, interpreted the results, and drew conclusions together (see Section 4.2 for details on collected data).

The workshop was structured as a narrative progression through four levels presented on an interactive online whiteboard. Each workshop opened with an introduction and a guide to the online whiteboard. Participants were then introduced to the core story: they had been chosen by a council of game masters and entrusted with a mission to investigate climate change and video games using real survey data (the Play2Act data set). They received objectives and a map visualising the four-level journey.

The first level, “New World Unlocked”, covered the survey background. It fostered a joint understanding of “green games“ through interactive discussion and presented the survey questions. Level 2, “Choosing Your Data Quests”, focused on developing research questions, termed data quests. An info box first explained question types, such as comparing groups or examining relationships between questions. Participants were then challenged to create ten collective data quests in twenty minutes. Each individual wrote quests on prepared post-its. Subsequently, a treasure chest of diamonds was revealed; each participant used two diamonds to vote for their favourite quest to be analysed next. Level 3, “Co-op Data Challenge”, involved analysing the data. Starting with the top-voted quest, a chart from a data dashboard created by GREAT partner PlanetPlay was presented for each prioritised question. Participants discussed what they found interesting or surprising and how the results connected to their experiences. Their interpretations could prompt follow-up quests for deeper understanding. In the final level, “Facing the Council of Game Masters”, participants reported back. They stated what they had learned, offered recommendations for action by the game world on climate change, and suggested questions for the next Play2Act survey. Screenshots of the whiteboard are provided in section 9.2.

These data workshops complemented the analysis by the GREAT research team, in the spirit of Citizen Science. They aimed to bring citizen science perspectives into a dataset originally gathered with the policy partner UNDP, where the public had acted only as survey respondents. Through the active engagement of players in the data analysis, the workshops generated new insights and recommendations on how games can contribute to climate action.

3.4 GCS7 Prosper

The Prosper case study applied the DiBL intervention through a game-based activity with university students at North-West University (NWU) in South Africa, an associated partner of the GREAT project. The case study was implemented from August 2024 to May 2025 and is reported in a case study report (Griffiths et al., 2026). The goal of the Prosper DiBL game was to promote understanding of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), foster self-directed learning, and gather students' attitudes on policy options. The Prosper DiBL was based on the pre-existing Prosper card game, an open educational resource developed by researchers at NWU.¹

The Prosper case study extends the DiBL intervention in two key ways: geographically, by being implemented outside the European Union, and methodologically, by transitioning a physical card game to a digital platform with new features. The case study also involved the South African Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment as a policy stakeholder to facilitate the uptake of findings at the policy level.

3.5 GCS8 UNDP Play2Act 2

Following GCS1 and GCS5, Play2Act 2 marks the third deployment of the PlanetPlay approach within GREAT (Harris et al., 2025). It adopted a similar method and question set to GCS5 but expanded on it in an important way: by using open-ended questions to capture in-depth insights into players' experiences with green game content.

The Play2Act 2 survey was run in partnership with 3 game studios, who promoted the same set of core questions. The second major extension of this study was its flexible design: game studios could add their own questions to the survey for their players. In practice, one studio chose to include two open-ended questions.

¹ <https://news.nwu.ac.za/nwu-launches-educational-card-game-prosper-mark-world-ip-day>

3.6 GCS 10 Beat The Heat

The Cyprus case study “Beat the Heat” applies the DiBL intervention through the co-design and piloting of a serious, dilemma-based game for primary school students (ages 10–12) within the context of climate education. The case study has been developed in collaboration with the Cyprus Ministry of Education, Sport and Youth, specifically through its Unit of Education for the Environment and Sustainable Development. The work was initiated in late 2024 and has progressed from exploratory design to pilot implementation.

The aim of the case study is to explore how games-based activities can support climate education under Cyprus’s Whole School Approach to Education for Sustainable Development (ESD), while also generating insights relevant to policy and practice. Early stages focused on identifying locally relevant climate dilemmas and assessing the opportunities and constraints of using games in Cypriot schools, including issues of digital infrastructure, classroom time, and teacher support.

The resulting game, *Beat the Heat*, focuses on urban temperature, outdoor comfort, and passive cooling strategies, with particular emphasis on green infrastructure in school and neighbourhood environments. The game uses visual, image-based prompts, such as aerial and thermal images, to support student reflection and decision-making about climate adaptation in familiar spaces. The game is being developed and tested using the DiBL platform, with technical input from the Cyprus Energy Agency to ensure alignment with national and EU climate objectives.

To ensure that game content remained technically credible and policy-relevant, the game and learning prompts were reviewed and developed with the Cyprus Energy Agency and the case study sponsor, the Unit of Education for the Environment and Sustainable Development (EESD). These stakeholders contributed expert reflections on the clarity of the climate adaptation concepts, the suitability of the dilemmas for primary education, and the alignment of the activity with sustainability education priorities, including the Whole School Approach. In addition, a stakeholder interview contributed an external GREAT-oriented perspective on the value and risks of using serious games as tools for youth-informed dialogue. Stakeholder feedback from the Unit of Education for the Environment and Sustainable Development (EESD) further confirmed the relevance of Beat the Heat as an implementation-oriented tool. EESD framed the collaboration as supporting teachers and stakeholders in operationalising existing national Education for Sustainable Development policy, rather than introducing a new policy agenda. They also noted

that, in Cyprus, ESD is intentionally delivered across subjects and does not rely on a single dedicated textbook, meaning teachers benefit from flexible, modular resources that can support classroom delivery. In this context, the DiBL game and associated facilitation materials were viewed as an additional, practical resource that can strengthen implementation through structured lesson design and classroom-ready prompts.

The Cyprus case study extends the DiBL intervention in two main ways: contextually, by adapting serious games for younger learners within a formal primary education policy framework, and thematically, by grounding climate dilemmas in spatial and environmental conditions experienced in everyday school settings. The case study also explores how game-based outputs can inform discussions on ESD policy implementation, positioning students as contributors to evidence on climate-resilient school environments.

4 Data, methods and analysis

The following table provides an overview of the data from the case studies presented in this report. It includes applied evaluation instruments, description, aims, nature and format of the data, and the main GREAT impact areas (defined in deliverable D5.1) the data contributes to, as presented in section 5 below.

Overall, we collected two basic types of data: qualitative and quantitative. The case studies collected a mix of both types, requiring systematic data triangulation. Data triangulation is a common research approach in social sciences, in which where multiple methods, data sources, or perspectives are combined to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the specific research issue.

In addition, reflective sessions in the consortium took place on a regular basis (bi-weekly) in the context of WP4 and a stakeholder reflection workshop organised by WP5. During these sessions, experiences from the cases were shared and recorded. These collective reflections were also incorporated in the following analysis.

Table 2: Data collection overview

Case study	Evaluation instruments used	Data description & main aim of the data	Data formats	Impact areas
UNDP Play2Act 1 – Data Workshops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participatory analysis of collected data Post-questionnaire Facilitator reflection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aimed to provide new perspectives on Play2Act1 data through a participatory and game-based approach Participants shared thoughts in a structured workshop through 4 main stages Participants provided feedback on their experience through four closed survey questions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Workshop recordings (audio and video) Online whiteboards (visual documentation) .xlsx export of the post-survey answers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participant impact Scientific impact Societal impact
Waterwise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Qualitative and quantitative analysis of post-questionnaires Qualitative analysis of stakeholder interview 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assessed experience of the game-based method and impact on psychological engagement Interview with Waterwise policy stakeholder on experiences from the DiBL game implementation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> .csv files .xlsx transcript of interview 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participant impact Societal impact Economic impact
UNDP Play2Act 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Qualitative analysis of open-ended survey responses Qualitative analysis of interview with representatives of games studios 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assessing innovative open-ended format as part of the PlanetPlay approach Informing impacts and assessing potentials of green game content Interviews with PlanetPLAY and games studios representatives about the process and impact 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> .csv files exports .xlsx transcript of interview 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participant impact Economic impact
Prosper	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quantitative pre- and post-questionnaire Qualitative post questionnaires 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Providing new insights into how the GREAT game-based approach can support self-directed learning and reflection on sustainable policies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> .csv export of pre- and post-survey answers .csv export of qualitative survey answers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participant impact
BeatTheHeat	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Qualitative analysis of stakeholder interview Post-questionnaire for participants Facilitator notes taken during the DiBL sessions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interview with EESD Unit policy stakeholder on experiences from the development of the 'Beat the Heat' DiBL Participants' evaluation of changes in their attitudes, and enjoyment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> .xlsx transcript of interview .csv export of post-questionnaire 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participant impact Societal impact

Case study	Evaluation instruments used	Data description & main aim of the data	Data formats	Impact areas
Cross-case studies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stakeholder analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collection of feedback from consortium partners about stakeholder impact via Mentimeter survey and discussion of results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> docx workshop documentation pptx results Mentimeter survey 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ALL

4.1 Data Analysis of GCS2 Waterwise

The Waterwise case study involved 19 participants who took part in the DiBL game between March and April 2025 across several online sessions. To evaluate outcomes, both quantitative and qualitative data was collected through two post-session questionnaires: one completed immediately after the DiBL session, and another distributed a week later. These questionnaires explored participants’ experiences of the DiBL and its impact on psychological engagement, focusing on discussion quality, collective efficacy, and changes in water use behaviour. The Waterwise case study therefore, offers valuable insight into the participant impact dimension. Main results from to the Waterwise case study have already been published in a conference paper (Watson et al., 2025), while this report focuses on interpreting the findings in light of the impact assessment.

The stakeholder interview with the Waterwise policy stakeholder was part of the 8 stakeholder interviews that formed the database for the qualitative content analysis (Mayring, 2000), which used a mix of deductive and inductive coding approaches. Two researchers were coding the interviews, focusing on the four impact dimensions of GREAT (participant, scientific, economic, societal).

4.2 Data Analysis of GSC5 UNDP Play2Act 1 – Data Workshops

The Data Workshops were implemented in two rounds. In the first round of implementation, 109 participants registered, but only four attended. Of those four, two were female, one was male, and one preferred to not indicate their gender. Three out of four had a high level of formal education (at least a Bachelor’s degree), while one participant indicated another form of education. Motivations for participating were diverse, though three out of four indicated that they had a desire to learn something new and to engage in a unique experience. Existing experience in data analysis was also very diverse.

For the second round of data workshops conducted with international computer science students based at a UK university, 31 participants registered and 27 attended. As only 3% of participants completed the pre-workshop form, we cannot derive their demographic information, motivations, or previous data analysis experience.

As part of the workshop implementation, we collected qualitative and quantitative data. Qualitative data consisted of participants' contributions collected during the workshops through recordings, the online meeting chat, and post-its. Broadly, data was collected on five main topics during the workshop:

- Participants' understanding of green games
- Participants' interests, curiosities, and open questions regarding the survey items
- Participants' perspective on the results of data analysis
- Participants' learnings during the workshop
- Participants' recommendations for action

All qualitative data were imported into a MAXQDA² project and analysed using qualitative content analysis (Mayring, 2000) in a mix of deductive and inductive coding. In deductive coding, codes are assigned to the data based on pre-defined concepts, frameworks, or research questions. In this case, the outcomes defined in our evaluation logic models as part of Deliverable 5.1 (Koller et al., 2024), as well as the workshop structure, acted as deductive guidance. In inductive coding, codes are assigned based on ideas, concepts, and insights emerging from the data.

Quantitative data consists of participants' responses to the post-survey. The post-survey included four questions taken from established scales: two covered experiences during the workshop, namely enjoyment of the activity (Markland & Hardy, 1997) and experience of the discussion (Schroeter et al., 2016), while the other two assessed psychological outcomes, specifically general science scepticism (Meier & Krämer, 2022) and collective efficacy beliefs regarding climate action (Castiglione et al., 2022). This quantitative data was analysed through visualisation of response frequencies and bi-variate correlations. For the visualisation of results, we distinguish between participants recruited from the global sample, who registered for the PlanetPlay platform (Round

² <https://www.maxqda.com/>

1, global sample, n=4) and the students at the GREAT partner UoB who were recruited as part of Round 2 (UK sample, n=27).

Moreover, unstructured internal reflections among the ZSI facilitator team provided insights into the feasibility, challenges, and potential of the method from a scientific perspective.

4.3 Data Analysis of GCS7 Prosper

Prosper involved 30 social science students from NWU, divided into six groups, alongside a control group of 45 students who participated in standard teaching methods. Evaluation combined quantitative and qualitative methods. Quantitative data were collected via a pre- and post-questionnaire based on a 5-point Likert scale, assessing self-directed learning across four dimensions: learning motivation, planning and implementation, self-monitoring, and interpersonal communication. The questionnaires were administered before the activity and five weeks after its completion. Qualitative data was gathered through an open-ended questionnaire with 20 prompts, supplemented by behavioural observations during gameplay. See Appendix for evaluation questions.

All data were collected and initially analysed by NWU, which performed statistical analysis of the quantitative data and thematic analysis of the qualitative data (Griffiths et al., 2026). For this report, ZSI further interpreted these findings to evaluate the case study's alignment with the participant logic model and its associated outcomes.

4.4 Data Analysis of GCS8 UNDP Play2Act 2

The Play2Act 2 survey collected both quantitative and qualitative data. Quantitative data consisted of the same survey questions already used in Play2Act 1 and reported on in D5.2 (Koller et al., 2025). Moreover, the GCS8 case study report includes a detailed analysis of the quantitative data (Harris et al., 2025).

In this assessment, we focused on analysing the two key open-ended survey questions:

- How did the green game content make you feel about climate change and nature issues?
- Have you changed anything in your daily life after playing green game content?

Qualitative responses were analysed using qualitative content analysis (Mayring, 2000) using a mix of deductive and inductive coding approaches. Following the literature review outlined in D5.1

Evaluation Framework (Koller et al., 2024) for deductive coding, we were interested in affective, cognitive, and behavioural dimensions of climate change engagement after playing a green game . We also identified attitudes and perceptions of using games for climate change engagement through inductive coding. The findings from Play2Act 2 feed into the assessment of logic model outcomes along the participant and the economic dimension.

For the analysis, we used the dataset available after the main promotion ended, which includes survey responses collected from 08.08.2025 to 16.09.2025. This represents 15,547 completed surveys. Out of these, 21% include responses to the first and 18% to the second qualitative question. However, many responses were not interpretable for the analysis, for example, because they were nonsensical, empty, or just contained sequences of random letters. As Figure 1 below demonstrates, irrelevant or uncodable responses made up 46% of all submitted responses, while 1.909 respondents provided submissions forming the basis content-relevant themes and codes, which will be described in section 5 of this report. Overall, this analysis distributed a total of 6.506 codes.

Figure 1. Overview of frequencies of all main themes, as % of respondents who expressed the theme. Sub-code frequencies are aggregated for the top-codes.

4.5 Data Analysis of GCS10 BeatTheHeat

The first stage of implementation of the GCS10 Beat the Heat involved 22 participants aged 9–12 in two face-to-face DiBL game sessions delivered in January 2026. The pilot consisted of two

classroom groups (11 + 11 participants) facilitated by the case study lead and research team of Frederick University in Cyprus. This phase evaluated the early outcomes of the DiBL activity in relation to GREAT's aims, focusing on engagement, age-appropriateness, and the extent to which dilemma-based gameplay could elicit meaningful youth perspectives on a locally grounded climate adaptation challenge.

Evaluation data were collected through multiple sources. Quantitative feedback was gathered via three short in-game questions completed at the end of gameplay, capturing self-reported enjoyment, willingness to play again, and perceived learning. Qualitative evidence was gathered through observation and facilitation notes, and teacher reflections on student engagement and discussion.

4.6 Cross-case Data Analysis

Alongside the analysis of the data collected in the specific cases, we also performed a data analysis across cases, which included qualitative interviews from case study stakeholders as well as a reflective analysis of stakeholder engagement done within the consortium.

4.6.1 Stakeholder Interviews

In collaboration with partners responsible for WP2, eight stakeholder interviews were conducted online. These interviews had a two-fold purpose: 1) they helped to understand the process of co-design and stakeholder engagement during the early steps in the GREAT research cycle. The insights are covered in the deliverable D2.3. And 2) the interviews also gave insights into the potential impact of the GREAT interventions as the stakeholders were asked about the perceived benefits and gains from participating in the case studies.

The methodology applied for the analysis of the interviews followed the qualitative content analysis described by , applying a mix of deductive and inductive coding. The deductive codes followed the defined impact areas from the GREAT logic model and the defined expected outcomes (see Deliverable 5.1: Koller et al., 2024). The inductive codes emerged from the interview transcripts.

This combination of inductive and deductive coding was applied to the transcripts by using MAXQDA³ software.

4.6.2 Stakeholder Analysis across Case Studies with consortium partners

In preparation for the *Impact Reflection on GREAT Stakeholders*, the GREAT Evaluation Team designed a Mentimeter⁴ survey (13. February 2025) to gather initial feedback and impressions from the consortium. The survey focused on the following questions:

- How important is this stakeholder for the success of the GREAT project?
- What added value does the GREAT project provide to this stakeholder?
- Are you currently in contact with this stakeholder?
- How could GREAT strengthen or formalize collaboration with this stakeholder?

These questions were posed for seven key stakeholder groups relevant to the GREAT project: climate experts, academic stakeholders, policy stakeholders, NGOs and campaigning organisations, citizens, educational stakeholders, and the game industry.

A total of 13 consortium partners began the survey, of whom 9 completed it in full. In the next step, the collected feedback was consolidated and collectively reviewed during the online session *Impact Reflection on GREAT Stakeholders* held on 18 August 2025. During this session, participants jointly discussed the survey results, reflected on stakeholder engagement strategies.

³ <https://www.maxqda.com/>

⁴ Online survey tool: <https://www.mentimeter.com/>

5 Results along the GREAT Impact Pathways

Table 3 below provides an overview of the total number of participants involved in each case study presented in this report as well as their sociodemographic characteristics (if available).

Table 3: Overview of participants considered in analysis.

Case study	Total nr. of participants	% female	% male	% prefer not to say	% non-binary	Age Range
UNDP Play2Act 1 – Data Workshops	1 st round: 4 2 nd round: 27	1 st round: 50% 2 nd round: N/A	1 st round: 25% 2 nd round: N/A	1 st round: 25% 2 nd round: N/A	1 st round: 0% 2 nd round: N/A	1 st round: 19-42 years 2 nd round: N/A
Waterwise	19	53%	47%	N/A	N/A	20–71 years, with a mean of 46 years
UNDP Play2Act 2	15,547 completed surveys	19%	71%	8%	2%	13–60+ years with 36 to 59 being the most frequent category
Prosper	30 participants involved in the DiBL activity	80%	20%	0%	0%	18-29 years, with a mean of 19.8
Beat the Heat	1 st Round: 22	50%	50%	0%	0%	9-12 years

5.1 Participant dimension of GREAT

The participant dimension focuses on the impact the GREAT methodology can have on individual actors involved in the activities. This can be mostly players, but also those participating in participatory processes of GREAT, such as data workshops or co-creation sessions, policy makers, and related stakeholders.

Figure 2. Logic model for assessing the participant dimension

5.1.1 Insights from GCS2 Waterwise

The evaluation of the **Waterwise case study** assessed participant impact across four key dimensions: the development of new means of expressing opinions, new means of participating in policy decisions, personal gains in knowledge, understanding, and awareness, and overall participant evaluation of the activity.

Findings regarding the outcome of fostering new means of expressing opinions were mixed. Immediately following the activity, most participants strongly agreed that the DiBL activity ensured arguments from all participants were heard equally, independent of status, gender, or age (see Figure 3). This indicates the activity’s design successfully created an inclusive environment for expression during the session.

Figure 3. New means of expressing opinions evaluated in the Waterwise case study.

However, data from a follow-up survey conducted one week later revealed that this impact did not sustain itself in daily life (see Figure 4). Participants reported highly varied experiences regarding increased discussion of water use after the Waterwise activity. Out of 19 participants, 7 agreed or strongly agreed that they discussed water use more, while 6 disagreed or strongly disagreed. This suggests that while the activity effectively facilitated in-the-moment expression, it did not consistently lead to continued dialogue on the topic outside the structured setting.

Figure 4. New means of expressing opinions evaluated in the Waterwise case study.

Furthermore, the activity demonstrated a positive impact on participants' sense of efficacy in policy engagement. A strong majority of participants agreed post-session that people can collectively have an impact on the water supply (see Figure 5). This points to successful improvement of participants' perceived capacity to contribute to collective decision-making processes related to water policy.

Figure 5. New means of participating in policy decisions evaluated in the Waterwise case study.

Regarding participants' personal gains, the findings suggest new learnings but mixed results regarding behaviour change. The findings of the pre- and post-comparison regarding self-reported water use suggest that approximately half of the participants did not change their behaviour. Among those who did report changes, actions included turning off running taps, taking shorter showers, and a general intent to be more water-efficient.

The findings indicate that the activity strongly influenced participants' awareness. In the one-week follow-up survey, most participants indicated they had been considering their water use more frequently since the session. However, compared to the impacts observed for expression and participation, this increase in consideration showed somewhat more variation.

Figure 6. Participants’ personal gains in knowledge, understanding, awareness, or attitudes evaluated in the Waterwise case study.

We also conducted a correlation analysis to explore relationships between these outcomes (see Table 4). A statistically significant positive association ($p = .02$) was found between participants who reported considering their water use more and those who believed in the potential for collective impact on water supply. No other significant correlations were identified.

Table 4. Heatmap of Spearman correlations for the Waterwise evaluation. Correlations significant at the $p \leq .005$ level are marked with *.

Since the zoom session, I have found myself considering my water use more	-			
Since the zoom session, I have discussed water use more	0.27	-		
Do you think we should be discussing our water use more?	-0.09	0.13	-	
Do you think collectively that people can have a big impact on our water supply?	-0.45	0.31	0.54*	-
	Since the zoom session, I have found myself considering my water use more	Since the zoom session, I have discussed water use more	Do you think we should be discussing our water use more?	Do you think collectively that people can have a big impact on our water supply?

Finally, participants also provided open-ended feedback on the aspects they enjoyed most and least, addressing the logic model outcome of positively evaluating their involvement in GREAT. Participants reported that the most enjoyable aspects of the activity were the interactive, game-based format, group discussions about water-saving habits and solutions, and specific components like the personal water use calculator and the Belton city scenario exercise.

The least enjoyable or most challenging aspects were specific creative tasks (such as creating a newspaper headline), technical difficulties, confronting personal water usage data, and the inherent challenge of prescribing water-saving methods for others.

5.1.2 Insights from GCS5 UND Play2Act 1 Data Workshops

The **data workshops of UNDP Play2Act 1** generated insights across all four participant-level outcomes defined in the logic model. These insights are based on two main sources: i) the final stage of the workshop, in which participants were invited to write what they had learned on post-

its, providing qualitative data; and ii) four questions in the post-questionnaire distributed directly after the workshop, providing quantitative data.

The findings indicate that the Data Workshops supported participants through new means of expressing opinions. This was evidenced through post-survey findings indicating that all respondents learned from others’ perspectives during the group discussions (see Figure 7). This question captures the capacity for mutual learning and the articulation of viewpoints, reflecting participants’ ability to express and exchange diverse opinions. Thus, the results suggest that the workshops acted as an enabling environment for constructive dialogue and deliberation.

Figure 7. Participants' assessment of the discussion during the data workshops.

The findings also support that participants gained new means of participating in policy decisions. This was examined through the concept of collective efficacy for climate action (see Castiglione et al., 2022). Within our evaluation framework, this construct operationalises the belief that society is capable of addressing climate change through collective efforts, which can be considered a necessary precondition for meaningful participation in climate-related policymaking. Post-survey responses (see Figure 8) showed that most participants felt strengthened in this collective belief after the workshops, suggesting a greater sense of capability for political participation. However,

one participant expressed disagreement, indicating that the impact on policy-related engagement may depend on prior dispositions or contextual factors.

Figure 8. Data workshop participants' self-reported collective efficacy beliefs.

Participants also positively evaluated their involvement in GREAT, which was assessed through the item “I enjoyed doing this activity”. This item was included as a direct measure of participants’ subjective experience and satisfaction with their involvement. All respondents reported enjoying their participation, with most expressing strong agreement (see Figure 9). These findings confirm the workshop’s perceived value among participants. Some participants (n = 6) also emphasised their enjoyment of the workshop on post-its, including two instances, praising the game-based design.

Figure 9. Data workshop participants' enjoyment of their participation.

Finally, the extent to which participants experienced personal gains in knowledge, understanding, awareness, or attitudes was explored in relation to science attitudes in the post-questionnaire. From a citizen science perspective, strengthened trust in science and its processes is a main goal. This is particularly relevant in the context of climate change, where variations in belief in the reality of climate change, as well as uncertainty and scepticism about its scientific foundations, remain widespread (Leiserowitz et al., 2023). Post-survey data revealed varying levels of science scepticism (see Figure 10): participants in Round 1 (global sample) displayed little scepticism, suggesting positive attitudes towards science, while those in Round 2 (UK sample) showed greater variation, with several expressing doubts about scientific work, even though they were university students. These results suggest that more than half of the participants did not express positive gains after the workshop, measured as reduced scepticism towards scientific work.

Qualitative data from the final part of the data workshop provides additional insights into participants' learnings. Accordingly, their main learnings were about green games and their potential, new perspectives on data and different ways it can be interpreted, and a better understanding of the limitations of the results.

Overall, the data workshops helped participants share their views, promoted discussion, and gave many a sense that collective action on climate is possible. Most found the activities rewarding, though the effect on science scepticism was limited.

Figure 10. Data workshop participants' self-reported general science scepticism.

5.1.3 Insights from GCS7 Prosper

The **Prosper case study** provides insights for all four outcomes specified in the participant logic model. In this section, we report on the findings relevant for our evaluation logic model outcomes, adapted from the analysis and findings presented in Prosper’s case study report by colleagues (Griffiths et al., 2026)

Firstly, the findings provide insights into participants’ improved means for expressing opinions. Qualitative feedback revealed that some participants developed better collaboration and explanation skills through problem-solving within the game:

“We teamed up with another group and shared the public–private bonus across SDG 7 and SDG 3” (Respondent 12)

However, quantitative survey results on interpersonal communication (i.e., presenting effectively or learning about fellow learners) showed no significant change from pre- to post-questionnaire, indicating the game did not increase participants' communication skills.

Further, we assessed the extent to which new means for participants to engage in policy decisions emerged by fostering understanding of policies and their consequences, strengthening motivation to participate in policy processes, and eliciting calls to action. Qualitative findings indicated that participants gained an understanding of policy consequences and motivation for civic involvement:

“Debating SDG priorities made me feel capable of drafting my own sustainability policy briefs.” (Respondent 20)

Students proposed economic incentives, such as improved feed-in tariffs for renewable energy and tax breaks for green jobs. They advocated for community engagement through town hall workshops and online co-design portals for sustainability projects. Reflecting on in-game disaster events, participants recommended infrastructure improvements like real-time flood alert systems and expanded public transport. They also emphasised youth empowerment through green start-up funds and integrating sustainability into the school curriculum. A few suggested policy monitoring mechanisms, such as digital hubs for tracking progress similar to those used in the game.

Another participants logic model outcome addresses personal gains in knowledge, awareness, and attitudes. In the quantitative questionnaire, participants reported improvements in self-monitoring and planning skills, feeling more confident in setting and managing learning goals, though there was no change in learning motivation. Qualitatively, students demonstrated increased awareness of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), with many able to recall specific goals and their relevance:

“Learning that boosting SDG 2 could hurt SDG 9 showed me real-world trade-offs between different goals” (Respondent 5)

Participants also exhibited systems thinking, recognising interconnections between policies and outcomes, such as how industrial decisions impact climate goals. Additionally, the game prompted reflective learning, with in-game events leading students to consider real-world implications and policies.

Participant enjoyment and engagement was also evaluated. Students reported being cognitively and emotionally engaged with the game content, found the tensions and trade-offs compelling, and experienced the activity as lively and dynamic.

In summary, the Prosper case study demonstrates that while the game did not quantitatively improve interpersonal communication skills, it still highlighted critical dimensions of participant-level impact: It effectively provided participants with new means to engage with policy decisions, fostered personal gains in knowledge and systems thinking, and was received as an engaging and dynamic activity. These findings indicate that the game served as a valuable tool for fostering policy awareness and strategic learning within an interactive context.

5.1.4 Insights from GCS8 UNDP Play2Act 2

The qualitative analysis of open-ended questions used in the **Play2Act 2 case study** provides evidence for impact by assessing participants' experiences with games with green content. The findings are structured around two core project outcomes: whether participants gained new means to participate in policy decisions, and whether they experienced personal gains in knowledge, understanding, awareness, and attitudes.

We first examine the extent to which engaging with green game content can empower participants with new means to participate in policy decisions. As part of the analysis, the theme of *efficacy beliefs* emerged, which is defined as a participant's belief in their ability to effect change, a crucial prerequisite for policy engagement. Two dimensions emerged from the findings: self-efficacy and collective efficacy, both appearing in participants' responses with similar frequency (see Figure 11).

Self-efficacy for climate action refers to an individual's belief in their capacity to act:

"It made me feel like I could do more to take care of our planet." (ID 37)

Collective efficacy reflects the belief that a group, nation, or society can act together to achieve meaningful climate action, as exemplified through these two quotes:

"Working with others towards sustainability" (ID 1040)

"I was glad to participate in some small way to be a part of a global initiative that truly could make a difference" (ID 547)

Within collective efficacy, some participants described a strengthened sense of collective identity, which describes the feeling of belonging to a larger movement or social group:

“It made me feel connected to a greater cause to help the planet” (ID 60)

Only one participant indicated they had lower self-efficacy:

“It felt like it was effective, but also there’s not much I can do on my own to improve the environment” (ID 812)

Likewise, one participant indicated feeling lower collective efficacy after playing green game content:

“It made me more aware of the issues happening on our planet but overall, did make me think that there was not much we could do to bring about change.” (ID 8934)

While fostering efficacy beliefs is an important step towards empowering citizens to engage in climate policy, the findings suggest that games do not serve as a direct tool for policy participation. Instead, green games act as a catalyst for building a sense of agency and, in the case of collective efficacy, for showing that others care and are willing to act (Fig. 10).

Figure 11. Frequencies of codes for efficacy beliefs as % of participants who expressed efficacy beliefs after playing games with green content. Sub-code frequencies are aggregated for the top-codes.

We also explored participants’ reported personal gains in knowledge, understanding, awareness, and attitudes. We used a framework of psychological engagement with climate change based on previous research and already outlined in D5.1 (Koller et al., 2024) that distinguishes three interconnected domains: cognitive, affective, and behavioural engagement.

Cognitive engagement after playing games with green content consisted of the sub-codes *raised awareness of issues and urgency*, *increased knowledge and understanding*, and *promoted reflection and new perspectives* (see Figure 12).

Figure 12. Frequencies of codes for cognitive engagement as % of participants who expressed cognitive engagement after playing games with green content.

Raised awareness was by far the most prevalent code related to cognitive engagement, ranging from general awareness to awareness of how one’s personal choices may contribute to accelerating climate change, awareness of environmental problems and their causes, or awareness of potential adverse future effects of climate change.

“Being a little more aware than I already had been.” (ID 14398)

„Being aware of how nature can change based on the actions of mankind“ (ID 13976)

“Giving us an awareness about whats really happening in our environment, and also giving us a chance to do good and help. Very grateful for it.” (ID 169)

Many participants also reported that by playing green games content, their knowledge and understanding of issues increased. This is different from just raised awareness, as in the code *increased knowledge and understanding*, participants emphasised learning something new, learning about facts, or being educated about issues, oftentimes in an actionable way.

“Educated me on the topics“ (ID 12437)

“Gave very useful information about climate change and how to recycle” (ID 574)

“It educates me on how to help the environment“ (ID 7739)

The third and least prevalent cognitive outcome was that gameplay promoted reflection and new perspectives. This code went beyond learning new facts and encompasses cognitive processes, whereby the green game content prompted critical thinking or a change in participants’ point of view.

*“The green game content made me really think about what was happening in our world.“
(ID 6616)*

„Made me think twice.“ (ID 6018)

„It made me change my vision about nature“ (ID 640)

“Changed my perspective i certain things. That our world needs to change.“ (ID 12418)

The next dimension of engagement, *affective engagement*, revealed a complex spectrum of emotional responses to green game content, including positive, negative, mixed, and critical emotional responses. Positive emotions were most prevalent, followed by negative emotions (see Figure 13).

Positive emotions include positive affective responses in relation to playing green game content and in relation to the topic of climate change or nature issues and encompassed several sub-codes.

Figure 13. Frequencies of codes for affective engagement as % of participants who expressed affective engagement after playing games with green content. Sub-code frequencies are aggregated for the top-codes.

Participants described an emotional connection to the subject matter:

“It made me feel deeply about climate.” (ID 11235)

The code connectedness to nature also appeared several times, describing appreciation and valuation of their environment, nature, and the planet after playing games with green content:

“Appreciation for the beautiful landscape of our planet” (ID 4534)

“Made me think about the beauty of nature and the need to protect it” (ID 2017)

Many reported feeling good about taking action and contributing to climate action:

“It provided me with satisfaction for contributing towards making our planet greener” (ID: 359)

A notable sub-code was *climate enthusiasm*, characterised by hope and optimism stemming from seeing others engaged and solutions presented.

“I felt like people care and see that it's an issue we should not ignore.” (ID 12083)

„It made me feel hopeful” (ID 14238)

“It's always beautiful to see people try to make a difference in any small way, it made me feel hopeful for humanity“ (ID 89)

Others simply indicated a general feeling good or said they felt engaged by the experience.

“It made me aware and feel like I was engaged.” (ID 7890)

Conversely, negative emotions after playing green game content were also common and multifaceted. These emotions generally arose from a recognition that climate change is a real and present problem, resulting in a negative reaction. These included anger directed at perceived inaction by leaders and corporations, guilt over personal impact, and feelings of isolation in caring about the issue.

“Angry I guess.” (ID 13437)

“I felt ashamed That we are not looking after our planet“ (ID 8392)

“I highly respect what you're trying to do. But this generation of younger kids ,teens,and adults really dont care about climate issues. Its sad but true.“ (ID 27)

Some participants expressed sorrow or sadness about environmental degradation, climate change, and its consequences:

“It is a sad since the environment suffers” (ID 7854)

“It made it feel real, and depressing. Exactly like it is. Well done i guess.” (ID 4436)

“It made me sad about what's happening to our world.“ (ID 6176)

A feeling of powerlessness, the feeling that there is not much that one can do about climate change, feeling helpless, difficult to understand what there is to do, was also expressed by few participants:

“Climate change is inevitable. We should stop seeding clouds and polluting, which makes everything worse.” (ID 5650)

The most common negative responses were expressing concern and perceived urgency, which includes worry about climate change and the recognition of the need for immediate action:

“Climate change is real and we need to act now.” (ID 1670)

“The green game content made me feel more aware and concerned about climate change.” (ID 793)

“That we need to take action before it’s too late“ (ID 8040)

For some, this tipped into anxiety, marked by fear and terror about the future:

“Scared for the way the world is moving.” (ID 8520)

“Terrified for all life on earth and all future life.” (ID 11126)

“It frightened me for the changes it could bring to the wild life and fish“ (ID 7561)

Few participants expressed mixed emotions, including feelings of uncertainty weirdness or ambivalence.

Finally, the comparatively least common emotional group in the affective engagement theme were *critical affective responses*. These included climate contempt, which is characterised by being tired of hearing about climate change, being annoyed to watch people being hysterical about climate change, or feeling angry that time and energy is spent on climate change.

“I dont care about the climate” (ID 1889)

“Nature is wonderful to be educated on. As for "climate change" and other propaganda is only a money laundering scheme. Not a single cent is every put towards cleaning cities or collecting trash off the side of the road.“ (ID 2377)

„To be honest, it annoyed me. It felt like I was being talked down to. And it also felt like a woke push by a liberal company.“ (ID 3959)

Responses such as feeling irritated or annoyed by the green game content were also a sub-code of *critical emotional responses*, in addition to climate reluctance, which describes the feeling that it is an important topic, but we, as a society, are acting too fast. Figure 14 provides an overview of the prevalence of all codes related to affective engagement.

Figure 14. Frequencies of all top-level and sub-codes for affective engagement as % of participants who expressed affective engagement after playing games with green content. Sub-code frequencies are aggregated for the top-codes.

The theme of *behavioural engagement and intentions* comprised three elements: *increased motivation for change, reported changes in daily life, and perceived barriers to action.*

Reported changes in daily life were the most frequent code, likely because of the survey question’s phrasing (“Have you changed anything in your daily life after playing green game content?”). The most common change by far was in *recycling, waste reduction, and resource conservation.* Other, less frequent changes included *sustainable consumption, social engagement and supporting organisations, sustainable mobility, and information seeking.* Notably, some participants mentioned very specific actions, such as installing solar panels, adjusting financial choices, or increasing recreational engagement with

nature. Overall, we identified 14 different types of behaviours that participants reported to have changed after playing games with green content, including a sub-code of *media and gaming behaviour*, which was *reduced gaming* and was mentioned once (see Figure 15).

Figure 15. Frequencies of all top-level and sub-codes for changed behaviours as % of participants who expressed changed behaviours after playing games with green content. Sub-code frequencies are aggregated for the top-codes.

Alongside these reported actions, many participants stated that the games increased their motivation for future behaviour change. However, this theme also included *perceived barriers to action*. Participants described obstacles such as limited financial means, a lack of local opportunities, or a belief that individual action is ineffective. This highlights a persistent gap between intention and implementation for some.

A final theme emerged related to the impact of playing games with green content: *no change*. This theme included six sub-codes (see Figure 16).

Figure 16. Frequencies of codes for no reported change as % of participants who expressed no change after playing games with green content.

The sub-code *external locus of control* covered views from participants who recognised environmental issues but felt their own actions had little effect against larger systems. For example:

“[...] I was aware of the greater impact that corporations had on our environment. Pollution and runoff from factories and trash from warehouses are far greater than that of those produced at the individual level.” (ID 5860)

“I know that I alone cannot achieve anything while large countries pollute the air without any consideration and greed.” (ID 8180)

The games did not change how these participants felt about climate change or behaved in daily life, as many saw corporations and governments as the real agents of change.

A stronger obstacle appeared in the sub-code *pre-existing climate scepticism and distrust*. These participants rejected the idea of climate change altogether, describing it as propaganda or a financial scam. For this group, the game’s message lacked credibility and could not influence their attitudes or behaviour regarding climate change. Interestingly, while some of these participants rejected climate change and climate action, they recognised the value of protecting the environment from threats such as pollution.

*“it didnt. i didnt buy the propoganda in the 90s as a small kid, im not buying it now .
companies spend millions to push a stupid agenda” (ID 289)*

*“Nature is wonderful to be educated on. As for "climate change" and other propoganda is
only a money laundering scheme.” (ID 289)*

*“While I do not believe in man made climate change. I do believe we have serious human
pollution of natural ecosystems that adversely affect us all in many ways (plastics,
petrochemicals).” (ID 2666)*

“Nothing has changed. Climate change/global warming is a farce.” (ID 4258)

Some extended this distrust to specific institutions or actors such as scientists:

*“I don’t trust any green organisations anymore since I’ve found out that they are a scam.”
(ID 4878)*

“Made me feel like some scientist is full of it.” (ID 9222)

*“Do you know who cares more about the environment? The people who are in it constantly
and depend on it to survive. I’ve never seen a scientist in the woods! Stop lying to ppl” (ID
12473)*

*“Climate, it has been a long time since it changed. All the governments have been lying to
us for years, doing their nuclear tests in Greenland. They prefer to spend money building
rockets to go to the moon instead of fixing things here.” (ID 15102)*

Related to explicit climate scepticism and distrust, some participants expressed resistance or active opposition to the use of games for green messages. Based on mentions like “woke”, this resistance seems to be related to right-wing political identity and the feeling of being influenced or manipulated.

“Yes. I’ve stopped playing them if they have a woke message.” (ID 3959)

“Not at all. More like made a decision to not support green woke companies” (ID 11378)

*“I have tried to avoid playing games that include a storyline that is irrelevant to the game to
try to influence a players viewpoint to align with or against a topic” (ID 13077)*

Some showed reactance in their responses, describing explicit anti-environmental behaviours:

“Yes I freely burn tires and styrofoam in my yard every week. I deposited all trash out the window to the side of the street. I would delete all and any “game” that wastes my time on this fake news.” (ID 5076)

“Burn more car tyres on my garden to keep warm and pour engine oil down my drains” (ID 7479)

Another form of limited engagement was coded as *unsure about changes*. Responses here were uncertain or indifferent, such as “Idk,” “Not sure,” and “I don’t know.” These comments suggest the game did not leave a strong enough impression to prompt reflection or lasting impact.

The sub-code *pre-existing pro-environmental identity or awareness* showed a different reason for any limited changes reported by participants. This code describes participants who already identified strongly with environmental causes and saw the game, if anything, only as reinforcement rather than as a key influence. Examples include:

“No I’ve always been as eco conscious as I can be in my daily life” (ID 336)

“I wouldnt say so, I recycle and try to be mindful of my impact but I did that regardless of a video game” (ID 732)

“I was already fairly conscious of efforts I could make in my daily life but it made me more determined to keep up with it” (ID 1187)

Finally, many brief responses to the two survey questions were coded as *no change in feelings or daily life – no reason given*. These were direct answers like “No,” “Nothing,” and “It didn’t.” Their number and simplicity highlight a general lack of perceived effect of green game content.

These findings highlight potential risks and limitations in using games as a tool for engaging citizens with climate change. While the proportion of respondents who indicated scepticism, distrust, or other negative reactions is very small – only 59 people, or ~2% of 3.348 – the intensity of their reactions is notable. Their reactions suggest that these participants perceive green games as political manipulation, leading to reactance, disengagement, or the reinforcement of existing scepticism and distrust.

Finally, to better illustrate the relative prevalence of the different engagement dimensions, Figure 17 presents the frequency distribution of the main codes across cognitive, affective, behavioural engagement and the category of *no reported change*. This overview reveals that green game content led to self-reported changes in pro-environmental behaviour almost as often as a lack of change was reported. Apart from behaviour, increased awareness of climate issues and their urgency was the most common positive outcome. The figure also makes clear that participants expressing critical or oppositional responses were a small minority within the sample.

Figure 17. Frequencies of all top-level and sub-codes for cognitive, affective, behavioural, and no engagement after playing green games as % of respondents who expressed any of these themes. Sub-code frequencies are aggregated for the top-codes.

5.1.5 Insights from GCS10 Beat the Heat

In the **Beat the Heat** case study, the participant dimension is applied in an age-appropriate manner for children aged 9–12, positioning students as emerging civic actors who can contribute perspectives on climate adaptation in school environments through structured facilitation.

Two open-ended reflection prompts were embedded in the game to capture changes in student thinking during the sessions. At the beginning of gameplay, students were asked *“How would you change your spaces (in your school) to make them more comfortable when it’s too hot?”* Responses from the first 2 pilots were dominated by immediate comfort solutions, most commonly air conditioning (32%),

water and pool related ideas (27%), fans (18%), and cooling treats such as ice cream (18%). Only 5% of students mentioned passive strategies including trees and shade at this stage. At the end of the game, students are asked, “*What changes would you want at your school, to make it cooler and more comfortable on a hot day?*” In these later responses, students most frequently proposed passive and nature-based cooling strategies, particularly trees or plants (68%), and shade or shading structures (27%), while AC continued to be mentioned, but this time only 18% of participants. This comparison suggests a shift from short-term cooling preferences toward more context-sensitive and low-energy adaptation ideas for school environments. Due to the small sample size of the first stage Beat the Heat sessions, these responses are interpreted as indicative of emerging awareness rather than evidence of retained learning and will be validated through further piloting.

Facilitator notes from the classroom pilots indicate that students engaged positively with the DiBL gameplay experience, they were willing to participate actively in the discussion and decision making. Participating teacher feedback further supports these observations, more specifically highlighting surprise at the confidence of students (especially the younger group ages 9-10) in expressing their thoughts and engaging with peers and facilitators. One student response suggested contacting “*a journalist or the press*” to create pressure for change, indicating early reasoning about civic influence pathways beyond the immediate classroom.

Participant evaluation was captured through Likert-scale questions at the end of the game. For the statement *I found the game enjoyable to play* 59% strongly agreed, 36% agreed and 5% (1 participant) disagreed and for the statement *I would be interested in playing a game like this again during future lessons* overall the responses were positive: 41% strongly agreed, 27% agreed, 14% somewhat agreed and 14% somewhat disagreed or disagreed. These findings suggest that participants perceived the game as enjoyable and worth repeating, indicating a strong level of engagement and perceived value as a learning and engagement activity. In addition, stakeholder reflections from an interview with an EESD representative reinforce the relevance of the participant dimension for long-term educational aims, noting that dilemma-based learning encourages “deep thinking” by requiring learners to take a position, consider multiple viewpoints, and practise informed decision-making and critical thinking. This was viewed as directly aligned with the goal of strengthening sustainability citizenship, understood as the capacity to make responsible decisions in relation to the environment and other people. In this sense, Beat the Heat supports not only climate learning content, but also

participatory skills associated with deliberation, problem-solving, and citizenship-oriented engagement.

5.1.6 Insights from the Stakeholder Interviews

Similar to these case studies, we also find evidence of the participants impact, such as new means of expression and participation, in the stakeholder interviews. The following statement summarises how the GREAT game-based approach can offer the general public a new and unthreatening way to voice their opinion and participate in an open policy agenda:

“The role-play dimension starts people thinking from that perspective and answering questions about something that maybe they never thought about before stepping into the room, but when they are given these options through the game, they start putting themselves in a situation where they want to have a say, they have an opinion. So this is a very useful process for us. The way it's done is not intimidating for people who are not usually very expressive. Because from my previous experience with game design, sometimes playful experiences can be intimidating to people who are not so outgoing, more introverts rather than extroverts. But this process that we tested with the GREAT project is not intimidating, it's something that you can enjoy easily jump into, and enjoy without feeling that you're over expressing yourself”. (SH1)

5.2 Scientific dimension of GREAT

The scientific dimension refers to the outcomes of the project, including contributions to an ongoing research agenda within the scientific community, new knowledge on engagement methods, and the development of new methodological approaches.

Figure 18. Logic model for the scientific dimension

The stakeholder interviews show some evidence of stakeholders seeing the GREAT approach as a new method for collecting opinions and attitudes from a diverse audience with scientific backing. While the statement below comes from a games studio, it includes a reference to the scientific value of GREAT:

There's also the funnel, which I think the GREAT project is a great example of, which is asking our players something that the politicians or stakeholders should know about, or can help them make better decisions, more informed decisions. So that's not towards the players, it's from the players. The more companies we can get involved, and the more scientific and academia led the findings, the better. Then it's not just a CEO agenda, but it's scientifically or statistically significant (I used to study economy economics). Then it's a better tool for those politicians who want the sound bites or who want to drive change, to actually get bigger stage presence. The best-case scenario is definitely that findings from studies like this actually make it to the news. (SH7)

Another interesting aspect of the collaboration between academic institutions, NGOs, and the games industry in the Play2Act series, from a scientific perspective, is how the methods were adapted and reshaped based on input from the different perspectives. Both NGO and games industry representatives highlighted their appreciation for their mutual collaboration, as well as for their collaboration with academia and the scientific backing of the approach. We consider this important evidence for how collaborative work has been successfully shaping an innovative survey method:

“So we added three features primarily to the service system. We added the ability to respond in a free form text way, either to a question or to a specific answer of a question to give more detail randomise the button order and we added the ability of the studios to the horizontal kind of button order to eliminate bias based on how big, how long your thumb is randomise the vertical order, so that your thumb distance isn't biasing which answer you pick. Studios to add their own questions at the end of the question block, before the demographic questions” (SH5).

Although PlanetPlay were initially very concerned about the inclusion of an open-text field in the PlanetPlay survey, a suggestion coming from the academic partners in GREAT, they were very pleased with the output. While they expected a significant number of spam answers, they were surprised that *“probably 95% or 90% plus, were legitimate people commenting, even if some of them are like short or or negative” (SH5).*

The data workshops, in which participants collaboratively analysed data from the UNDP Play2Act 1 case study, also supported three main outcomes on the scientific dimension of impact: they contributed to an ongoing research agenda by developing new questions, provided new information and data on the climate crisis for domain experts, and informed citizen science approaches and their application.

Firstly, the participatory data workshops emerged as an effective method for **extracting new research questions and insights** and provide future directions for the scientific understanding of green games and climate engagement. The questions raised by participants cover key areas including demographic differences across urban/rural, age, gender, education, and country/region; outcomes and impacts of playing green games covering cognitive, emotional, and behavioural aspects; features, elements, and mechanisms underlying green games; motivation and engagement for gaming green, and practical applications.

Demographically, participants raised essential questions about how age, gender, formal education, and nationality influence individuals' climate attitudes and behaviours. For example, they asked how players in the UK differ from those in Nigeria in their perception of climate change, or whether being in school or having formal education influences hope or awareness regarding environmental issues. This highlights the importance of research designs that consider diverse social and geographical contexts.

Regarding mechanisms and features, participants were interested in how specific game elements, such as in-game rewards or prior climate awareness, influence motivation, behaviour, and emotional responses. They questioned which game mechanisms are most effective for climate education and how initial awareness might influence gameplay. This focus suggests that future research should examine causal pathways that link game design choices to individual change in more detail.

In terms of outcomes, participants explored the cognitive, emotional, and behavioural impacts of green games. They questioned whether playing such games leads to increased environmental knowledge, improved mental health, changes in concern for climate issues, or actual change in day-to-day behaviour. Emotional aspects such as feelings of hope or powerlessness were also highlighted as potentially significant factors influencing engagement with climate games.

The motivational and engagement theme included participants' curiosity about why certain groups (e.g., older adults) choose to engage, or rather, not engage, with green games, and what factors drive sustained motivation. Questions about how feelings towards climate change, such as hope or powerlessness, relate to game engagement also emerged.

Finally, many participants were interested in practical insights on how to measure the impact of green games and increase their uptake, especially among underrepresented groups. They asked for recommendations on spreading green games, strategies to engage specific demographics, such as older people, and ways to track the measurable outcomes of gaming interventions.

In terms of scientific impact, this participatory approach adds value by integrating citizens' perspectives in the analytical process of global data requested by a policy institution. Through the participatory process, in which participants are seen as experts rather than academics, new questions emerged that might be missed in more traditional researcher-led analyses. This

methodology can promote reflexivity in the scientific process and help align research agendas with the concerns and experiences of diverse participants. This method also supports the generation of actionable knowledge by combining empirical data with collaborative interpretation.

Secondly, the collective analysis and interpretation of results **provide new information and data on the climate crisis for domain experts** (outcome no. 2 in the scientific logic model).

Data workshop participants discussed the findings by examining group differences and possible factors influencing behaviour. They highlighted that many elements beyond green games may influence behaviour change, such as peer influence, being in an educational environment, or having greater awareness of one's actions. Participants noted which results they found most interesting or surprising, particularly the numerous country-level differences revealed in the Play2Act survey, which spans around 180 countries, and the strong interest of younger players in green or purpose-driven games.

Participants also identified several limitations of the survey. They recognised sample bias and the uneven distribution of responses, with underrepresentation of people with lower formal education and older adults. They suggested this bias might be due to the survey's distribution method via games, which these groups play less often. Participants further noted that the honesty of self-reported responses could not be verified.

They also discussed gaps in the data, such as the limited inclusiveness of video game-based survey distribution (as evidenced by the underrepresentation of certain groups). They called for ways to better engage underrepresented groups. Another gap concerned perceptions of green game quality, i.e., whether respondents found the green games engaging, boring, or acceptable, which could influence behavioural outcomes. This was not measured in the survey, but is important to understand the impacts of green games, according to data workshop participants.

Suggestions for future research included exploring how game attributes and characters affect player responses and examining individual motivations for playing green games. Participants recommended studying the devices used for gaming and the ways players connect game experiences with real-world environmental issues. Understanding why and how players recommend green games to others could also provide new insights. Expanding survey reach in developing countries and repeating surveys periodically would improve representativeness and track behavioural changes

over time. Research should identify which games have the most significant impact and why, while adapting approaches to better reach excluded groups. When working with older adults, tailored questions and game designs matching their interests should be developed. Further study is needed into how external factors, such as weather, influence feelings about climate change and motivation to play. Open-ended questions in future surveys can capture more detailed and reflective responses.

Together, these findings expand understanding of climate engagement through games and provide domain experts with new information on behavioural, inclusivity, and new directions for influencing climate awareness and action through games, provided by a diverse group of workshop participants and gamers. Moreover, the data workshops produced a concrete contribution to an ongoing research agenda. Students from the University of Greater Manchester, who participated in the second round, were inspired to further analyse the workshop data; they published a conference paper offering novel insights and results (Iwendi et al., 2025).

5.3 Economic dimension of GREAT

The economic impact of GREAT activities is likely to benefit the commercial partners in the project (SGI and PlanetPlay) and contribute to the business propositions of these partners, while potentially being leveraged by the gaming industry. In the long-term, the learnings from the GREAT project can contribute to the shaping of new green visions for game-based approaches and the games sector overall.

Figure 19. Logic model for economic dimension

The analysis of the open-ended responses from the Play2Act 2 case study revealed essential insights for the games industry and directions for promoting green messages or developing games with green content. Specifically, the findings allow assessing the logic model outcome of using game-based methods as a new, innovative approach for the gaming industry and for benefiting society in the context of climate change. The findings are structured around three core thematic areas that emerged from the coding process, each with key sub-codes (represented in Figure 20): *Potential and positive affordances of green games*, *What green games should do*, and *Criticism and limitations of green games*.

Figure 20. Frequencies of key topics as % of participants who expressed any attitudes towards green games. Sub-code frequencies are aggregated for the top-codes.

Potential and Positive Affordances of Green Games

The findings suggest support for the notion that games can be leveraged for societal good. Overall, eight subcodes emerged in this topic (see Figure 21).

Figure 21. Frequencies of sub-codes of potential of green games as % of participants who expressed potential of green games.

Participants frequently cited the potential for real-world impact, describing how well-designed games could reduce perceived distance to the topic of climate change and motivate action:

“A well-designed green game can make climate change feel less like a distant “news story” and more like something immediate, personal, and solvable, which is a big step toward motivating real-world change.” (ID 519).

This sentiment aligns directly with the project’s aim of involving citizens. Furthermore, one of the most prevalent sub-codes within this theme was *raising awareness*, indicating general agreement that games serve as a powerful tool for educating and informing the public. Additional positive affordances often mentioned included the provision of new knowledge and the enjoyable and engaging nature of green game content, which also emphasises the motivating and pleasant characteristics of games and their capacity for fostering positive feelings towards the topic. Many participants also emphasised that they appreciated the fact that game studios address and speak up about such important issues, for example:

“Made me respect the game developers choices in putting world issues inside the game, raising awareness for topics that should be discussed” (ID 300).

Less frequently mentioned, were sub-codes covering games’ potential for *raising funds*, *enabling communication*, and *games can act as motivation tools*:

“Everyone is aware. So telling them is just a waist of time. But raising funds it more active and affective. In my opinion.” (ID 13896)

“I thought it was a good way to send a message” (ID 3269)

“I can't say that I have changed a lot just by playing games, but it can be one of the contributing factors which motivates to take one step more towards saving the environment” (ID 1051)

Overall, positive attitudes towards games were the most prevalent of the three main topics, providing a solid foundation for the innovative application of games for societal benefit:

“It broke the stigma and made me feel good about the game and myself. It gave me purpose!” (ID 5424)

What Green Games Should Do

Beyond acknowledging the potential of green games, participants also outlined future directions and suggestions for improving their use and application. Three key sub-codes emerged (see Figure

Figure 22. Frequencies of sub-codes of what green games should do as % of participants who expressed what green games should do.

22).

First, they called for greater outreach to amplify impact, as green game content is not common or prevalent:

“It’s important to spread the message as far and wide as possible” (ID 6320).

Second, and as most common sub-code, participants emphasised the need for better and fact-based design of green game content in order to be taken seriously as tools for education and awareness-raising:

“The one game I played with green fundraising didn’t include much info on the issue” (ID 3360)

Finally, though only voiced as explicitly by one participant, games should move beyond focusing on individual behaviour change and instead concentrate on targeting systemic actors, such as corporations and governments, who hold greater responsibility for environmental outcomes:

“I am not contributing to climate change – the world’s governments are! [...] You need to be bounding and attacking THEM!!!” (ID 7046).

This last point challenges the “games for good” model as simplistic and too focused on citizens, calling for involvement of policy stakeholders.

Criticism and Limitations of Green Games

Relatedly, several participants also engaged critically with the question of green game content: six sub-codes emerged that may present challenges to the notion that green games can be an innovative approach that benefits society (see Figure 23).

Figure 23. Frequencies of sub-codes of limitations of green games as % of participants who expressed limitations.

A primary concern was the view that green content was often too basic or non-actionable, leading to doubts about its capacity for real-world impact:

“It was very basic info that I already knew and agreed with” (ID 172).

A major criticism voiced by participants related to perceptions of hypocrisy and greenwashing. Participants questioned the sincerity of game studios, which were noted as large polluters themselves, in promoting environmental messages, seeing it as mere marketing and a new way of generating profits:

“It made me think it is just another money earning scam for the development team.” (ID 8939)

“It didn’t make me feel any different I would rather see head lines saying Ten Square GAMES CO-operates with other gaming platforms to donate millions to climate change in 3rd world counties” (ID 1334)

Other criticisms related to the user experience of games with green content. Participants argued that the green games they played were characterised by poor or unrealistic design, bad or uncredible messaging, and intrusive content that disrupted their gameplay and made the experience unenjoyable:

“It made me uninstall the game.” (ID 9202)

“I was not sure the information the game was putting out was real” (ID 7688)

“Living in the real world as a farmer and than playing one in a game, [...] it’s not the same. Crops don’t grow fast, raising them is back breaking. And the taxes are harsh. (ID 6827).

One of the most prevalent codes in this topic was *Escapism*: many participants explicitly stated they play games for fun and relaxation – for distracting from reality - and were not interested in any political or educational content.

“I play Subway Surfers to help relieve stress” (ID 1044)

“Not much impact...gaming for fun” (ID 3823)

This also suggests that deploying green games can drive certain target groups away, possibly depending on their initial views on climate change and climate policy.

“I hated it , I’m trying to play a game and escape the politics of the world” (ID 2964)

“Kinda weird, I just wanted to play the game not be an activist” (ID 5573)

“[...] Games are meant for fun and not for social or political purposes.” (ID 6211)

Overall, the findings from Play2Act2 suggest mixed support for the economic impact dimension. The findings reveal support for the potential and positive affordances of green game content,

validating the core idea of using games for societal benefit to some extent. The suggestions for future directions of green games can shape this innovative approach and facilitate real-world impact. However, participants also expressed substantial criticism, particularly regarding messaging, design, perceptions of “political” messaging in games, greenwashing, and the credibility of the games industry as a promoter of green messages. The findings indicate that the proposed approach is not universally welcomed and carries reputational and design risks for the industry, while the industry should take its contribution to pollution and climate change seriously.

Again, we also find evidence of the potential economic impact of the GREAT approach in the stakeholder interviews. Most prominently, various stakeholders stress that through the GREAT-initiated engagement with the players, they were able to learn about their users which can contribute to their user profiling and help them in the future to make more specific offers to their target groups, especially with a focus on green content. This applies to both GREAT approaches, the large-scale survey via PlanetPlay, as well as the more qualitative engagement via DiBL. In the case of PlanetPlay, one of the very dedicated games studios added their own questions around what would encourage their players to do more green game content; they wanted to get information about what parts of their game ecosystem they should encourage, leaderboard, special events and similar activities. The CEO confirms their interest in players behaviour and the fact that GREAT offered them an opportunity to find out more about their player, which in the end may give them an advantage in terms of their future business activities:

I like the idea that we can put purpose into the game, and that we can do things with the game, so we want to try as many initiatives as possible and also see what resonates with the players. Where do the players think it was cool we did this activation and where do they perhaps turn off? (SH7)

Although smaller in numbers, richer in details, we also get confirmation that the role-play approach in DiBL can provide important consumer insights for the stakeholders as this statement from the Waterwise case study shows: *But when it comes to what people think and how they use, that's really just such golden information for us. And that helps us understand what we can do better to engage our customers. (SH4)*

A policy stakeholder expressed that the approach of reaching gamers worldwide through collaboration with game studies is more cost-effective than hiring a polling company. Previous experiences with launching large polls required much greater effort on their part. This again confirmed the benefits of the collaborations that we established in GREAT between the main three

stakeholder groups, namely academia, civic society, and the games industry. Although it needs to be mentioned that from a purely economic perspective, the measurable benefits within the GREAT trials were not equally spread across the stakeholders. While the games company did not report any direct ROI from a financial point of view, the NGO clearly confirmed that for them, it was less expensive and much faster to receive such a great amount of global data via GREAT than with other surveys they had launched previously.

Finally, although this was not defined as a core outcome in our logic model, we find evidence in our data that the GREAT approach contributed to some of the games companies' missions and their Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR). In the case of SYBO, our most prominent collaborator from the games sector, the commitment to environmental responsibility has a strong backing from the CEO, who is a strong promoter in the games industry and tries to bring environmental issues on the agenda of CEOs. One of the employees summarises the importance of the companies' mission in the following way:

I think the biggest thing for us is the alignment of the mission. The ability to educate or inspire a younger audience through games to understand the importance of the environment, of pollution and of all that coming together. Engaging with them is more of a personal aspect, but we've also made that a corporate mission to be more socially impactful and to generate awareness. We define civic engagement in the mix there. (SH3)

5.4 Societal dimension of GREAT

At the societal level, we expect the GREAT outcomes to be of considerable value for policy makers, public organisations and NGOs, as we offer insights and a new method to engage with citizens for targeted communication, participation, engagement, and opinion gathering. In addition, we expect that the GREAT toolkit and policy briefs will provide policymakers, NGOs, and campaigning organisations with a new understanding of the potential of games for societal change and transformation.

Figure 24. Logic model for societal dimension

The 8 stakeholder interviews are an important source for identifying the potential societal impact the GREAT results can have. Most importantly, we get confirmation from stakeholders across the different case studies that they see clear benefits of the **innovative game-based approach method** that were piloted in GREAT. The positive statements on the method equally come from the school context as well as the broader public engagement. For the dilemma intervention, this seems to work and is appreciated in different contexts. From an educational setting in schools through the Beat the Heat case study, we hear that:

“I really like that aspect of this project because if you have a dilemma, it makes people think you have to give an answer to something that is a dilemma. It gives up people the opportunity to do some deep thinking. And in order to do some deep thinking and make a decision, you would need to also practise the skills of being informed, so you would do research. You would try, hopefully to see all things considered and hear different views and opinions and also practise using your critical thinking skills. And that's a very good added value of this project that it's building it. Like the fact that you're building learning on the dilemma is very powerful for education, but also in the long run. For the purposes of the project, I think or I would like to hope that it contributes to creating an informed, sustainable citizenship. So, I really liked it. I like the aspect of the how it's structured on dilemmas. And problem solving too.” (SH1)

Likewise, we hear from the Waterwise case study stakeholder that:

“I like the idea of the playful discussions. I think quite often, as a company, the way we do things is we do a customer survey. It's going to be research, we're going to have an incentive for someone to complete the survey and that's what we're going to do. It gets information which is great, but we don't get great engagement and I just wonder if that's the best way to try to get a really broad picture. Because sitting to do a survey doesn't seem like a lot of time, but are we getting the best responses? Are we getting the best cross section of our customers? Is it touching everybody? I think engaging in a different way was kind of the real thing for me here. I'm really interested to see if we get different results.” (SH4)

Given the positive resonance on the method, the stakeholders also confirm their interest in the **exploitation** of the method and the specifically generated dilemma games as Open Educational Resources (OERs). In the following statement we see some confirmation to use the method in the future:

“Using a playful experience as a way to consult specific groups, to have focus groups and to use it as a participatory tool, or an engagement tool. It provides an alternative way to reach out to stakeholders. We are interested in that because we work in multiple ways. Sometimes we host events, or we create architectural installations that may attract people to provide input on spaces on the city or different urban subjects. But this more indoor way to interact with stakeholders is something that we didn't explore enough, because we normally work outdoors in public spaces. This was something that we could do in a classroom with stakeholders in person in the offices from specific authorities. So, it provided a way to reach out to different audience in a different way.” (SH6)

The Green Jobs dilemma game (documented in D5.2) has already been provided as an **OER** in an Austrian participation portal⁵. In the following statement, another stakeholder refers to the Beat the Heat dilemma game also being offered as an OERs as it aligns well with the national school curriculum:

“To incorporate the elements of citizenship or sustainability citizenship inside the curriculum, using Beat the Heat and all the other tools. Of course, after being translated in Greek, it will be great if there is a connection enriching the resources that we make available to teachers, and they can take them and use them either from our website or direct them to those websites to be used.” (SH1)

⁵ <https://partizipation.at/praxisbeispiele/great-green-jobs-fallstudie/>

Next to the specific exploitation of the dilemma games and the game-based methods of GREAT we have learned that a very important effect of the project activities has been the **awareness raising** amongst a large population on environmental aspects. We can see confirmation of this impact across cases and stakeholders. This again holds true for the large outreach via PlanetPlay, where a global audience can be reached, as well as the more dedicated and deeper awareness raising with the dilemma game approach. For the latter, we have evidence that people changed their behaviour, such as water use reduction in the Waterwise case study, while for the former, we hear e.g. from the CEO of SYBO that *what we have been exploring with UNDP, it's clear that when we activate the numbers go up. And answers have come in from regions that have not necessarily answered surveys before. And awareness raising has also been a core aspect of the UNDP as they confirm: "Well, benefits, I would say would be to raise awareness on different topics, like promoting dialogue, engaging with people, building this habit of engaging with citizens in certain areas or topics, et cetera"* (SH8).

An important factor from a policy perspective and policy buy-in is the fact that the project is well aligned with policy goals. This have been confirmed by various policy stakeholders engaged in the case studies:

So, for me, the benefit, the biggest benefit of the of the collaboration was the production of the materials and the fact that the teachers can use them. I see that the project is corresponding with existing policies covering what is brought forward from the project. (SH1)

That element fits very well into our agenda. As I mentioned before, this is not the first polling exercise that we have conducted or launched, and our efforts are also to put climate change and nature action, the discussions, onto the agenda of governments, but also of citizens (SH8)

The data workshops, in which participants collaboratively analysed findings from the UNDP Play2Act 1 case study, also contribute to understanding the societal impact dimension of GREAT. Participants developed conclusions and recommendations based on the Play2Act 1 data, highlighting how GREAT activities test new approaches to engaging citizens through gamified participation (outcome 1 in the societal logic model) and deepen understanding of the transformative potential of such participation for societal change (outcome 2).

Participants suggested leveraging the broad reach of games to raise awareness and integrate climate change narratives that educate, promote action, and inform about possible solutions. They stressed

the need to develop more games that promote climate action and use diverse platforms to reach different audiences, regardless of educational background, while encouraging long-term player involvement. Game studios should align their game content with region-specific challenges to account for the fact that countries in the global north and south face differing priorities and necessary actions.

Participants also underlined the overall potential of games to raise awareness about climate issues across social and demographic boundaries, to educate on pressing environmental challenges, and to drive behavioural change. They valued collaborations between the game industry and climate initiatives aimed at promoting climate awareness and environmental protection.

In conclusion, the data workshops show that game-based approaches, such as the GREAT activities, can play a meaningful role in advancing societal transformation goals such as climate action and public engagement.

6 Discussion

The data collected across all the GREAT case studies revealed clear indications of impact and benefits from the GREAT methods across all four impact areas and the involved stakeholders, while also identifying challenges and barriers for a wider take-up. Policy makers, NGOs and game companies have been defined as core stakeholders in the project design and core beneficiaries of the project outcomes, next to the involved players/citizens. However, none of these core stakeholders formed part of the consortium and were e.g. not financially compensated for their time. And those with funding streams, such as the policy stakeholders, lacked time for close engagement. The implications of this imbalance have already been discussed in deliverable D2.3. We structure our discussion here along the different stakeholder groups in GREAT and focus on the observed impact as well as associated barriers and challenges.

The consortium's internal stakeholder reflection identifies several key areas where stakeholder involvement can be strengthened, thereby enhancing both the project's sustainability and overall impact. Across the GREAT project, several challenges and opportunities have emerged in relation to stakeholder engagement. **Policy stakeholders** are essential to the project, yet engagement remains uneven and mostly limited to local or regional levels. The consortium partners saw a risk in overwhelming policymakers if communication is not carefully managed. Opportunities for a more balanced communication include setting up regular policy briefings, developing policy-oriented outputs such as white papers, and creating a policy advisory council to strengthen long-term collaboration. Part of this has been taken on and its effects have already been shown in the stakeholder uptake of some of the case study results.

However, we have also experienced barriers for policy stakeholders in communicating the results of the case studies, especially when the results are not on the priority list of the policy stakeholders. The difficulties of communicating or exploiting the collected data from the case studies stemmed partly from the findings themselves and whether they aligned with political priorities, and partly from the way in which the data was collected. For example, we experienced that the collaboration with the game industry was considered carefully and critically, and may have been an issue of trust for some policy stakeholders. Collaborations with the private sector can be challenging for governments and require careful consideration.

Citizen engagement has been limited and short-term, largely tied to individual game sessions without ongoing communication or structured feedback loops. The Play2Act data workshops were an attempt to engage citizens in the data interpretation process more deeply and revealed that such an involvement can lead to new insights and trigger further research. As pointed out in D2.3, citizens were not sufficiently involved early in the co-creation process of the case studies. Opportunities include establishing citizen advisory panels, appointing community ambassadors, involving citizens earlier in design processes, and offering open-access resources that encourage long-term participation. A clear barrier has been the lack of financial compensation or other types of incentives, especially in the case where intrinsic motivation may be limited. Nonetheless, we saw in the case studies very clear indications of impact at the participant level. Accordingly, the GREAT methodology improved citizens' awareness, promoted collective efficacy, and provided new means of expressing opinions and engaging with policy processes. However, these positive impacts were often not sustained beyond the specific GREAT activity. Especially changes in behaviour – in contrast with changes in attitudes – were often inconsistent among participants. While the positive impacts among participants were prevalent, a minority reported negative reactions, scepticism, or resistance to game-based engagement. This also highlighted potential limitations in reaching different audiences through GREAT's methods. Overall, the impact assessment along the participant dimension reveals that GREAT effectively fostered initial engagement with climate change and policy dialogue. In contrast, long-term influence – especially on real-life climate action – found limited support.

Educational stakeholders face similar challenges, with sporadic engagement and a lack of explicit materials. In the future, the project could increase support for educational stakeholders by providing teacher toolkits, open educational resources, training programmes, and regular communication to support curriculum integration. Those case studies where educational institutions were involved, such as Green Jobs or Beat the Heat, where GREAT interventions were implemented in public schools, have provided us with evidence that educational institutions appreciate the game-based approaches and see value in the OER that GREAT brought forward.

For **NGOs and campaigning organisations**, engagement has been confined to a few case studies and broader networks remain underused. Strengthening collaboration through partnerships with larger NGO networks, co-hosted events, capacity-building activities, and tailored toolkits could

create significant added value. However, one of the participating NGOs also stressed their limited possibilities in creating wide impact as they do not have the mandate to create policy changes.

Domain and climate experts, although originally identified as core stakeholders for the GREAT project, have been only minimally involved. This is due to the fact that they have not been systematically identified or integrated into project processes. Given the focus on reaching policy stakeholders and NGOs, the need to involve additional domain experts was less pressing for the case studies. There is also no evidence in our data for apparent effects on this stakeholder group. However, the project partners still see an opportunity in establishing a formal expert advisory panel and involving them earlier in co-creation and evaluation activities for specific interventions in the future. The data's trustworthiness could clearly be better supported by the involvement of more domain experts.

Academic stakeholders, which partly overlap with the domain and climate experts mentioned above, faced challenges due to limited external involvement and competing academic priorities, but as a consortium, we see a potential for expanding the academic network, increasing joint publications, and formalising collaboration through academic working groups. The core academic partners in GREAT clearly benefitted from their engagement, and the scientific impact of the project has been demonstrated along various outcomes, including the co-development of an innovative game-based survey methodology. Participatory data workshops generated novel research questions, advancing the agenda on green games and game-based climate engagement. The project contributed directly to ongoing research, inspiring further academic analysis and publication. These outcomes illustrate the value of the GREAT methodology and provide a foundation for expanding academic networks and informing future directions.

Finally, **industry stakeholders**, especially within the game sector, were engaged primarily through a commercial partner, limiting broader industry uptake. Long-term interest and wider outreach for the GREAT approach remain uncertain. An important challenge for game studios is the fact that they do not want to “bother their players” with something not directly part of the game and especially if it gets them away from the game. Many of their players do not want to be distracted from their game, or else they would not return to that specific game. This would leave a negative economic impact on the game company. So, while the involved game studios clearly found the GREAT approach a valuable opportunity to learn more about their players, which can help them

with player profiling, they also see issues with the implementation and need a clear call to action for their players.

Fortunately, the games industry has realised the importance of supporting the climate agenda, and its players are committing to the cause. The Playing for the Planet Alliance⁶, co-initiated by the consortium partner PlanetPlay, is supported by global game studios, trade association and industry supporters. The opportunities identified by the consortium for future impact include expanding industry partnerships through sector associations, developing joint innovation projects, and formalising collaboration through partnership frameworks, such as the Playing for the Planet framework.

⁶ <https://playing4theplanet.org/>

7 Conclusions

Earlier findings outlined in the mid-term evaluation report D5.2 already highlighted GREAT's approach as a promising and scalable method for engaging with complex societal challenges around climate change. This final impact assessment report consolidates the overall conclusions of the GREAT project.

The mid-term evaluation emphasised key strengths: the GREAT activities achieved considerable global reach, particularly through its game-based data collection, while the dilemma-based formats promoted in-depth policy discourse and explored policy solutions in smaller settings. The mid-term evaluation also identified critical limitations, including demographic bias and possible risks of digital exclusion, which highlight challenges in inclusivity. In this section, we refine these initial assessments based on the final impact assessment results and outline the following integrated conclusions.

In general, GREAT activities fostered public engagement with climate change issues and policy, achieved meaningful learning outcomes, promoted reflection, and reached diverse audiences. The DiBL format provided a non-imitating environment for in-depth discussion and successfully engaged citizens in policy discourse. This posits the DiBL intervention as a viable method for complementing traditional participatory and citizen engagement activities. However, it is also resource-intensive and not readily scalable to larger communities, and it faces recruitment challenges. In turn, the PlanetPlay approach achieved wide outreach and collected enormous quantities of data. It can provide policymakers, NGOs, and campaign organisations with a deeper understanding of how video games can foster societal transformation, bridging gaps in awareness and motivating public engagement on climate action. Yet, the results showed that this approach also carries several risks of triggering negative affect, being perceived as too political by gaming communities, or being perceived as greenwashing leveraged by the gaming industry. Overall, concerns about the diversity of engaged players, and thus, the demographic and digital inclusivity of the GREAT approach, remain. A broad reach through online games does not automatically ensure inclusive participation.

We also identified key lessons and directions for future work. Game-based approaches require additional efforts to ensure inclusivity. Targeted outreach activities are required to recruit diverse participants, and methodologies should continuously be adapted to ensure inclusivity. Equal

participation is critical for the legitimacy and validity of game-based approaches for climate change, and they should not reinforce existing biases but actively engage diverse and marginalised groups.

Relatedly, involving stakeholders – from players to policymakers – early and sustainably is crucial to create ownership and ensure effective communication. Especially the short quantitative engagement represented by the PlanetPlay approach requires precise framing and messaging to avoid any perception of manipulation. A hybrid approach that combines small-scale, in-depth activities with broader outreach appears promising, but such an implementation could not be implemented within the evaluation timeframe, as the Waterwise case study is still ongoing.

Overall, the GREAT research cycle process is highly dependent on external actors and stakeholders, which proved difficult across the various case studies. As pointed out in D2.3. The intensity of collaboration with stakeholders (especially policy stakeholders and games companies) has been lower than had been hoped for, which shows some of the limitations of our studies.

We recommend future research to build on the findings in GREAT and further explore how game-based approaches can be adapted to avoid replicating exclusion and instead offer new perspective for greater inclusivity. Equal participation is needed for legitimisation of game-based approaches, and this required further methodological adaptations. In addition, and related to the impact on individuals and society at large, we recommend more in-depth examination of causal pathways that link game design choices to individual change, as we have identified the overall potential of game-based approaches for climate awareness, influence motivation, behaviour, and emotional responses.

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9 Appendices

9.1 Evaluation instruments used in Waterwise case study

9.1.1 First post-survey

How was your experience of the session??

(5-point scale rating between "Very Negative" - "Very Positive")

Which aspect did you enjoy the most?

(Free text entry)

Which aspect did you enjoy the least?

(Free text entry)

What did you learn about your water use?

(Free text entry)

Do you think collectively that people can have a big impact on our water supply?

(5-point scale rating between "Strongly Disagree" - "Strongly Agree")

During the discussions, were the arguments from all participants equally heard, independent of their status, gender or age?

(5-point scale rating between "Strongly Disagree" - "Strongly Agree")

9.1.2 Second post-survey

Since the zoom discussion, have you made any changes to how you use water in your daily life?

(Free text entry)

Since the zoom session, I have found myself considering my water use more *(5-point scale rating between "Strongly Disagree" - "Strongly Agree")*

Since the zoom session, I have discussed water use more *(5-point scale rating between "Strongly Disagree" - "Strongly Agree")*

9.2 Data Workshop Materials

A CALL FOR ADVENTURE IN THE WORLD OF DATA

LEVEL 1: NEW WORLD UNLOCKED

Level 1: Data creation overview

How was this world created?

Backed by science

PlayStation has partnered with UNESCO and 250+ game publishers supported by the 100 UNESCO project, to connect gamers' opinions and voices to policy makers globally.

Using games the power to be heard by world leaders when it comes to climate action.

Participating Games

Play 2Act Survey Promotions

100% 188 180k

Level 1: Data overview

Lots of data to discover

Do you think video games can play a role in solving climate change or environmental issues?

43.53 % Yes

27.22 % Maybe

29.25 % No

After playing green game content, have you changed anything you do in your day-to-day life?

44.91 % Yes

34.02 % Maybe

15.71 % No

What is your gender?

51.08 % Male

35.9 % Female

10.1 % Prefer not to say

2.92 % Non-binary

How old are you?

42 % 18 to 25

28.19 % 13 to 17

16.58 % 36 to 50

10.76 % Prefer not to say

2.47 % 60 or over

How do you feel about climate change and nature issues?

27.84 % Worried - worried about the situation

21.42 % Concerned - concerned about the long-term future

16.55 % Frustrated - frustrated about how I can help

10.85 % Disappointed - disappointed in how action

8.42 % Hopeful - optimistic about the future

7.57 % Indifferent - my issue is not this one

7.83 % Not sure

Have you heard of any of the following agreements or plans?

48.04 % Paris Agreement

40.53 % Rio Climate Change Agreement

15.42 % Montreal Montreal Protocol

15.33 % Montreal Protocol

11.67 % Kyoto Protocol

How old were you when you left education?

34.78 % 21 or over

23.38 % 20 or over

18.92 % 17 to 19

11.22 % Prefer not to say

6.94 % 10 to 16

3.71 % Under 12

1.05 % Never went to school

adventure
a burning
hat's yours?

LEVEL 2: CHOOSING YOUR DATA QUESTS

Level 2: Choosing data quests

Data Quest: Do younger people like more games than older people? (Use data to support your answer.)

Data Quest: Do people in Australia and Germany feel different about climate change?

Data Quest: Is there a connection between the way parents can help their children change and knowing about climate change and the environment?

Comparing groups

Looking at countries

Relationships between survey questions

SOME INSPIRATION: DIFFERENT TYPES OF DATA QUESTS

Comparing different groups 🧑🏻‍🦱 🇺🇸 🇩🇪

This type of data quest looks at how different groups of people answer the same survey question.

- Do younger and older people answer differently?
- Do people with different genders respond differently?
- Does the time someone finished their education make a difference in their answer?

Looking at countries 🇺🇸 🇩🇪

This type of data quest looks at differences between countries.

- How do people in one country answer a particular survey question?
- How do answers compare between two or more countries?

Relationships between survey questions 🧑🏻‍🦱 🇺🇸 🇩🇪

This type of data quest explores connections between survey questions.

- If someone gives a certain answer to one question, what do they say on another?
- Are there patterns between different responses?

I dare you to find the *least likely* data quest.

Can you create a quest so wild, the data starts questioning you?

Which burning question is keeping you awake at night?

What's the most obvious data quest? Low-hanging fruit is still fruit!

What's the one theory you'd love to prove—or totally destroy—with the data?

Can you come up with a question no one else in the room is asking?

LEVEL 3: CO-OP DATA CHALLENGE

Level 3: Data Challenge

What did you find interesting about this quest?

What do you think about this result?

Does anything surprise you about these results?

Which other ways are there to interpret these results?

How do these results connect to your own experiences?

Level 4

**FINAL LEVEL:
FACING THE COUNCIL OF GAME MASTERS**

**THE SCROLL OF TRUTH:
WHAT HAVE YOU LEARNED TODAY?**

**THE SCROLL OF TRUTH:
WHAT SHOULD THE GAME WORLD DO ABOUT CLIMATE CHANGE?**

**THE SCROLL OF TRUTH:
WHAT QUESTIONS SHOULD GUIDE OUR NEXT SURVEY?**

9.3 Evaluation instruments used in Prosper case study

These research instruments are also reported in the Prosper case study report.

9.3.1 Pre- and post-questionnaire

Question	Item
1	I know what I need to learn.
2	Regardless of the results or effectiveness of my learning, I still like learning.
3	I strongly hope to constantly improve and excel in my learning.
4	My successes and failures inspire me to continue learning.
5	I enjoy finding answers to questions.
6	I will not give up learning because I face some difficulties.
7	I can pro-actively establish my learning goals.
8	I know what learning strategies are appropriate for me in reaching my learning goals.
9	I set the priorities of my learning.
10	Whether in the school practicum, classroom or on my own, I am able to follow my own plan of learning.
11	I am good at arranging and controlling my learning time.
12	I know how to find resources for my learning.
13	I can connect new knowledge with my own personal experiences.
14	I understand the strengths and weakness of my learning.
15	I can monitor my learning progress.
16	I can evaluate on my own my learning outcomes.
17	My interaction with others helps me plan for further learning.

18	I would like to learn the language and culture of those whom I frequently interact with.
19	I am able to express messages effectively in oral presentations.
20	I am able to communicate messages effectively in writing.

9.3.2 Prompts used in qualitative questionnaire

“Can you describe your experience playing Prosper? What aspects were engaging or challenging?”

“How did the collaborative elements influence teamwork?”

“Which mechanics/features best held your attention?”

“How did Prosper impact your understanding of sustainability/SDGs?”

“Which SDG issues/solutions resonated and why?”

“How did the SDG focus influence your thinking about real-world challenges?”

“Did Prosper motivate you to explore sustainability independently?”

“Did the game encourage SDL behaviours (e.g., goal-setting, reflection)?”

“How did you approach collaborating to address challenges?”

“Did you have to negotiate/compromise to find solutions?”

“In what ways did the game foster/challenge problem-solving?”

“How relevant are the skills/knowledge to real-world efforts?”

“Which ideas could you apply outside the game?”

“What, if anything, was confusing or could be improved?”

“Suggestions to make Prosper more accessible/effective?”

“Adaptations for age/skill levels?”

“What changes could improve feedback/visibility of impacts?”

“Policy implications from the dilemmas you faced?”

“Policies/actions that would be effective (examples welcome)?”

“How could government better support community collaboration?”